

Decomposition of Phenol and Naphthol Ethers by means of Concentrated Hydrochloric Acid.

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Ethers decompose to some extent when heated with halogen acids. Hydriodic acid at its boiling point decomposes most ethers. Concentrated hydrobromic acid also decomposes ethers to a considerable extent at a high temperature (Stoermer, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 321; Kolhatkar, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1918, 2, 179) found that anisole and phenetole undergo slight decomposition with 19 per cent. hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 100°.

The present investigation was undertaken to study the influence of different substituent groups in the benzene ring on the decomposition of phenolic ethers when heated in sealed tubes with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The following ethers were used in the investigation—anisole, phenetole, *ortho*- *meta*- and *para*-(nitro-, chloro-, bromo-, amino-, methyl- and acetyl-) anisoles, *p*-chloro- *p*-bromo- and *p*-nitrophenetoles ; 2:4:6 tribromoanisole ; 2:4- and 2:6-dinitroanisoles ; methyl ethers of α - and β - naphthol and methyl ether of aromatic tetrahydro- α -naphthol.

The solid ethers were carefully purified by crystallisation and the liquid ethers by fractional distillation. Mixtures of ethers and concentrated hydrochloric acid were introduced in hard glass tubes (1 cm. dia. and 25 cm. length). The tubes were sealed and kept in a bomb furnace for two hours at 130°.

Preliminary experiments were carried out to study the action of concentrated hydrochloric acid on aromatic ethers. Aromatic ethers were heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid in sealed tubes at 130° for some hours. The reaction mixture was then made alkaline, and the undecomposed aromatic ether was extracted with ether and its weight was determined. The alkaline solution (after extraction with ether) was made acidic and the liberated phenol was extracted with ether and its weight was also determined. This weight was found equal to that calculated on the assumption that in the

action of hydrochloric acid on aromatic ethers only phenols are formed. The liberated phenol was also identified by appropriate tests.

The decomposition which the ethers suffered was determined in most cases by estimating the liberated phenols. A mixture of potassium bromide and potassium bromate, in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid, brominates readily a large number of phenols and the amount of bromine taken up is usually quite definite. *p*-Nitroanisole, and *p*-nitrophenetole did not react with bromine. The phenols in these cases were estimated by the bromination method in presence of the ethers. In other cases, as the ethers react to a certain extent with bromine, the undecomposed ethers were first extracted in an alkaline solution by ether. The phenols were then estimated. In the case of *m*-bromophenol, 2:4:6-tribromophenol and the three aminophenols, the bromination method does not give good results. The undecomposed ether in these cases was directly estimated after separation from the phenol by extraction with ether in a strongly alkaline solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Experiments to show that bromate-bromide mixture can be satisfactorily used for estimating phenol, alone and when mixed with anisole. 1 C. c. of bromate-bromide mixture liberated 0.0192 g. of bromine.

Estimation of Phenol.

Phenol	Bromate-bromide mixture added.	0.1N-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ for back titration.	Bromine used up.	Calculated amount of bromine.
0.10 g.	30 c.c.	8.3 c.c.	0.5096 g.	0.5106 g.
0.05	20	60.2	0.2544	0.2553
0.04	20	22.5	0.2024	0.2040
0.02	10	11.3	0.1016	0.1020
0.01	10	177.	0.0504	0.05106

One molecule of phenol uses up 3 molecules of bromine.

Estimation of Phenol in a Mixture of Phenol and Anisole.

Since anisole reacts with bromine, the former was removed by extraction in an alkaline mixture by ether and the phenol estimated as before.

Phenol.	Anisole added.	Bromate-bromide mixture added.	0.1N-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ for back titration.	Bromine used up.	Calculated amount of bromine.
0.1 g.	0.1 g.	30 c.c.	8.3 c.c.	0.5096 g.	0.5106 g.
0.05	0.2	20	16.1	0.255	0.2553
0.05	0.15	20	16.1	0.255	0.2553
0.02	0.1	20	35.3	0.1016	0.1021
0.02	0.1	20	35.3	0.1016	0.1021

Agreement between the amount of bromine used up and that calculated on the basis that one mol. of phenol uses up 3 mols. of bromine, justifies the use of this method in the estimation.

Estimation of the Decomposition of Anisole after Treatment with Hydrochloric Acid.

0.5 G. of anisole with 6 c.c. of 10N-hydrochloric acid was heated in a sealed tube at 130° for 2 hours. The phenol liberated during the decomposition was then estimated as above and the results obtained are given below.

Expt.	Bromate-bromide mixture added.	0.1N-Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ required for back titration.	Phenol liberated.	Percentage decomposition of the ether.
I.	50 c.c.	30 c.c.	0.141 g.	32.4
II.	"	31.5	0.1386	32
III.	"	31	0.131	32
IV.	"	30.5	0.1402	32.3
V.	"	30	0.141	32.2
			Mean	32.22

Similar procedure was followed in the case of most ethers.

The following procedure was followed in the case of ethers where bromate-bromide mixture did not give satisfactory results.

Estimation of m-Bromoanisole in a Mixture of m-Bromoanisole and m-Bromophenol.

m-Bromoanisole is estimated by extracting it with ether from an alkaline solution. The ethereal solution is evaporated and then the ether directly estimated by weighing.

Weight of <i>m</i> -bromoanisole taken.	Weight of <i>m</i> -bromophenol added.	Weight of <i>m</i> -bromoanisole found.
0.5 g.	0.2 g.	0.496 g.
0.5	0.1	0.498
0.4	0.3	0.3975

Agreement between the values of *m*-bromoanisole estimated and that actually taken justifies the use of this method in the estimation of *m*-bromoanisole, when treated with hydrochloric acid.

Estimation of the Decomposition of m-Bromoanisole after Treatment with Hydrochloric Acid.

A mixture of 0.5 g. of *m*-bromoanisole and 6 c.c. of 10*N*-hydrochloric acid was heated in a sealed tube at 130° for two hours. The phenol liberated during the decomposition was then estimated by the above method and the results obtained are given below.

Bromate-bromide mixture added.	0.1 <i>N</i> -Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ required for back titration.	Phenol liberated.	Percentage decomposition of the ether.
0.5 c.c.	0.491 c.c.	0.010 g.	2.1
0.5	0.489	0.011	2.2
0.5	0.488	0.012	2.4
			Mean 2.23

Tabular Summary of Results.

Ether. 0.5 g. taken)	Percentage decomposition suffered at 130°.		Percentage decomposition at 100° with 10 <i>N</i> -HCl (6 c.c.).
	with 10 <i>N</i> -HCl (6 c.c.).	with 5-HCl (6 c.c.).	
1. Anisole	33	—	—
2. Phenetole	14.8	—	—
3. <i>m</i> -Nitroanisole	6.4	1.3	1.27
4. <i>o</i> - "	10.83	1.95	1.9

Tabular Summary of Results—Contd.

Ether. (0.5 g. taken)	Percentage decomposition suffered at 130°		Percentage decomposition at 100° with 10N-HCl (6 c.c.).
	with 10N-HCl (6 c.c.).	with 5N-HCl (6 c.c.).	
5. <i>p</i> -Nitroanisole	12.77	2.4	2.3
6. <i>m</i> -Chloroanisole	3.55	—	—
7. <i>o</i> - „	9.9	—	—
8. <i>p</i> - „	12.8	—	—
9. <i>m</i> -Bromoanisole	2.23	—	—
10. <i>o</i> - „	4.67	—	—
11. <i>p</i> - „	6.3	—	—
12. <i>m</i> -Methylanisole	11.4	—	—
13. <i>o</i> - „	12.1	—	—
14. <i>p</i> - „	16.1	—	—
15. <i>m</i> -Aminoanisole	12.0	—	—
16. <i>o</i> - „	35.5	—	—
17. <i>p</i> - „	75.0	—	33.25
18. <i>m</i> -Acetylanisole	12.0	—	—
19. <i>o</i> - „	53.8	—	—
20. <i>p</i> - „	68.3	—	8.8
21. 2 : 4-Dinitro- anisole	5.4	—	—
22. 3 : 5-Dinitro- anisole	3.3	—	—
23. 2 : 4 : 6-Tribromo- ansiole	3.7	—	—
24. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenetole	5.34	—	—
25. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenetole	6.3	—	—
26. <i>p</i> -Bromophenetole	3.5	—	—
27. <i>p</i> -Methylphenetole	5.4	—	—
28. Methyl ether of α -naphthol	15.7	—	—
29. Methyl ether of β -naphthol	26.8	—	—
30. Methyl ether of α . tetrahydro- α -naphthol	9.2	—	—

Discussion of Results.

(1) *m*-Derivatives decompose to the least and *p*-derivatives to the greatest extent, the corresponding *o*-compound having an intermediate value.

(2) Acidic atoms or groups like Br, Cl, NO₂ increase the stability of the ethers. Acetyl group, however, is an exception while methyl group behaves like an acidic radicle.

(3) Ethyl ethers decompose less readily than methyl ethers.

(4) Increase in the number of negative substituents increases the stability of the ethers.

(5) α -Naphthol methyl ether is less stable than its tetrahydro-derivative.

(6) Amino-group lessens the stability of the ethers.